

Degradation of pharmaceutical and food colourant using electrochemical technique

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Brilliant blue FCF disodium salt of 4-{4-*N*-ethyl-*m*-sulphobenzyl aminophenyl} (2-sulphonium phenyl)-methylene} [1-(*N*-ethyl-*N*-*m*-sulphobenzyl)- Δ^{2-5} -cyclohexadienimine] is a certified colourant used by various pharmaceutical companies. In the present work, the study of electrochemical behaviour was carried out and feasibility of controlled potential electrolysis technique is judged in terms of rate of disappearance of colour, decrease in absorbance, disappearance of any reduction peak in decolourised solution, decrease in COD value which were chosen as parameters to evaluate the progress of reduction. The decomposition products of controlled potential reduction were characterised by spectrophotometric and chromatographic methods. This method of dye degradation is useful in identifying the reduction pathway and provides potential for dye degradation.

The gravity of the colour pollution problem caused by the dye colours is increasing due to the unabated, indiscriminate and careless disposal of the coloured effluents from various industries. Recent studies have shown that the dyes, which impart such intense colour to water bodies, have been reported to have toxic effects. Though the concentration of dyes present in water is as low as 1 ppm, it causes allergy and are even carcinogenic and mutagenic in nature.

Thus appropriate treatment of dye wastewater to remove colour and dye compounds is important. Currently, the most widely used physical method is adsorption by activated carbon but it creates huge amounts of sludge, which becomes a pollutant on its own creating disposal problem^{1,2}. Direct photolysis has not been found to be effective in the degradation of azo dyes and biological degradation is also found to be slow for most of the synthetic dyeing classes^{2,3}.

Electrochemical methods can be successfully applied for the treatment of coloured effluents with efficiencies as high as 90% thus enabling further biological treatment⁴. The degradation of synthetic dyes specially azo reactive dyes has been studied by other workers using different electrochemical technique such as electrochemical bleaching of dye in an electrolyte solution containing halide ion as the activated ion⁵, decolourization of azo dye in an anaerobic baffled reactor⁶ and decolourization of azo dye, tartrazine, by controlled potential electrolysis⁷. But the electrochemical studies performed on the triphenylmethane dyes discuss mostly the analytical applications. Polarographic reduction of triphenylmethane dyestuffs were also the subject

of various investigations⁸. However, no systematic and comprehensive study could be found in literature on the electrochemical behavior and decolourization capability of brilliant blue FCF. In the present paper, the electrochemical study has been carried out on the commercially used triphenylmethane dye, brilliant blue FCF disodium salt of 4-{4-*N*-ethyl-*m*-sulphobenzylaminophenyl}(sulphoniumphenyl)-methylene} [1-(*N*-ethyl-*N*-*m*-sulphobenzyl)- Δ^{2-5} cyclohexadienimine] [A]. Brilliant blue FCF is commonly used food colourant and find extensive use in candies, bakery products, cereals, puddings, beverages, dry powdered drinks, also in gelatin desserts, ice-creams and frozen desserts. It is also a certified pharmaceutical colourant used by various leading pharmaceutical companies. It is used as colourant in antacid tablets and in cough syrup in combination with tartazine (colourant)⁹.

Results and discussion

Cyclic voltammetry :

Cyclic voltammetry of brilliant blue FCF was performed at platinum and steel foil electrodes in the pH range of 2.5–

12.0 and in aqueous neutral medium. The voltammograms in aqueous neutral medium at varying scan rates (50–1000 mV s^{-1}) showed two peaks in the cathodic scan and two peaks in reverse scan (Fig. 1). Two peaks obtained referred

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of brilliant blue FCF ($4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ in distilled water) at platinum working electrode at varying scan rates (mVs^{-1}): (1) 50, (2) 100, (3) 150, (4) 200, (5) 500, (6) 1000.

to two different reduction steps preceded at the electrode surface. As the scan rate (ν) was increased, the cathodic peak potentials ($-E_{p,c}$) shifted in negative direction and the anodic peak potentials in positive direction indicating irreversible electron transfer¹⁰. The plot of $i_{p,c}$ vs $\nu^{1/2}$ (ν = scan rate) in aqueous medium (distilled water) and at pH 7.9 are found to be straight line passing through the origin indicating diffusion controlled nature of the reaction taking place at the electrode-solution interface¹¹. While the plot of peak current vs $\nu^{1/2}$ at pH 2.5 is found to be deviated from the origin indicating electrode reaction to be mainly diffusion controlled with some adsorption contribution (Fig. 2). The adsorption complications were further supported by the increase in peak current function with scan rate (i.e. i_p / γ_2 vs $\log \gamma^{12}$).

Both cathodic and anodic peak potentials showed negative shift with increasing pH up to pH 7.9 thereafter, there was a little change in $E_{p,c}$ with pH. This led to the conclusion that proton transfer precedes the electrode process. Above pH 7.9, the $E_{p,c}$ becomes independent of pH due to the reduction of unprotonated species as equilibrium shifts towards unprotonated form. The break in linearity at pH 7.9 corresponds to the $\text{p}K_a$ value¹⁴. The cathodic peak current showed decrease with increase in H^+ ion concentration indicating that rate of protonation decreases and irreversibility increases with increasing pH¹⁵.

Fig. 2. Plot of $i_{p,c}$ vs $\nu^{1/2}$ of brilliant blue FCF solution: (I) in distilled water, (II) pH 2.5, (III) pH 7.9 at platinum foil working electrode, concn. = $4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$.

Controlled potential electrolysis:

Controlled potential electrolysis of $4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ solution of brilliant blue FCF dye was carried out at electrolysis potential of -1.20 V . With steel as working electrode the reaction took $\sim 4 \text{ h}$ for complete decolourisation (Fig. 3). With

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammograms of brilliant blue FCF ($4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ in distilled water) at steel working electrode, scan rate 200 mV s^{-1} : (1) before electrochemical treatment, (2) after electrochemical treatment.

Pt foil the reaction time was $\sim 8 \text{ h}$ (Fig. 4). After exhaustive electrolysis at both the working electrodes no cathodic peak could be observed in the voltammograms recorded indicating the absence of any electro-active species present in the

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammograms of brilliant blue FCF (4×10^{-4} M in distilled water) at platinum working electrode, scan rate 200 mV s^{-1} : (1) before electrochemical treatment, (2) after electrochemical treatment.

electrolysed solution. Similar trend was observed on controlled potential electrolysis of dye solution at different pH. The dye solution after controlled potential electrolysis covering the entire pH range did not show any reduction peak and current also got reduced to background level indicating reduction of chromophoric group (Table 1). Coulometric measurements were carried out to calculate the number of electrons taking part in the overall electrode process and were found to be six.

Table 1. Voltammetric characteristics of brilliant blue FCF at different pH before and after electrochemical treatment

Sl. no.	pH		$-E_{p,ci}$ (V)	$-E_{p,cii}$ (V)	$-i_{p,ci}$ (μA)	$-i_{p,cii}$ (μA)	$E_{p,a}$ (V)	$i_{p,a}$ (V)
1.	2.5	A	0.573	0.744	349.9	412.1	0.342	173.5
B			-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	3.8	A	0.634	0.708	222.6	330.0	0.452	174.3
B			-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	4.5	A	0.726	0.861	262.5	302.3	0.441	178.7
B			-	-	-	-	-	-
4.	7.9	A	0.880	0.620	116.9	80.0	0.324	65.84
B			-	-	-	-	-	-
5.	10.5	A	1.018	0.665	95.19	3.36	0.619	53.84
B			-	-	-	-	-	-
6.	12.5	A	0.961	0.665	188.3	30.0	0.705	136.8
B			-	-	-	-	-	-

A = Before electrochemical treatment, B = after electrochemical treatment.

Redox mechanism :

On the basis of cyclic voltammetry, controlled potential electrolysis, coulometric measurements, chromatographic

and spectral studies, the reduction mechanism of the compound under consideration is depicted in reaction Scheme 1. As per the reaction scheme, reduction of the triphenylmethane dye [A] proceeds in two stages involving 6 electrons. In the first stage the quinonoid form is converted into benzinoid form by intake of two electrons and two protons to form [B].

In the second stage the -C-N- bond attached to two benzene rings is cleaved by intake of two electrons and two protons individually resulting in the formation of three products [C], [D] and [E] (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Spectral studies and rate kinetics :

The UV-Visible spectra of brilliant blue FCF dye were recorded in the region 350–650 nm, in aqueous medium as well as in B.R. buffers at varying pH. The λ_{max} of the dye solution is 620 nm. The progress of electrolysis was monitored by recording spectral changes at different time intervals. The decrease in the absorbance of the intermediate species with time was used to evaluate the kinetics of the reaction. There was gradual decrease in absorbance with time. Absorbance later becomes practically parallel to the base line. The kinetics of decolourisation was also monitored and it was found to be varying with initial dye concentration. The resulting Abs vs time plot was found to be exponential in nature. A linear plot of log absorbance vs. time indicated that decrease in colour and absorbance obeys first order rate expression. The value of the first order rate

constant determined at different pH and aqueous medium are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Comparison of 1st order rate constants for electrochemical reduction of brilliant blue FCF on platinum and steel working electrodes

Sl. no.	pH	Working electrode used	Initial applied potential vs SCE (V)	Concn. (M)	K $k_{\text{abs}}/\text{min}^{-1}$
1.	Distilled water	Steel foil	-1.20	4×10^{-4}	8.8×10^{-3}
2.	Distilled water	Platinum foil	-1.20	4×10^{-4}	6.6×10^{-3}
3.	2.5 pH	Platinum foil	-1.20	2×10^{-4}	2.8×10^{-3}
4.	7.9 pH	Platinum foil	-1.20	2×10^{-4}	2.3×10^{-3}
5.	10.5 pH	Platinum foil	-1.20	2×10^{-4}	2.5×10^{-3}

Chromatographic studies :

Attempts to separate the electro-reduction products were carried out following conventional controlled product electrolysis (CPE). After CPE the electrolysed solution was subjected to thin layer chromatography using dioxane : water (8 : 2) system. Two spots were obtained along with one coloured spot of the initial coloured dye solution on the silica gel chromatographic plate as evident from the reaction mechanism.

Chemical oxidation demand (COD) :

Electrolysed solution shows decrease in COD value of initial coloured solution (4×10^{-4} M) from initial 3120 mg dm^{-3} to final 430 mg dm^{-3} . Almost 86.35% of COD reduction was observed. This could be ascribed to the electro-reduction of the initial dye into decomposition products leading to decrease in COD value.

Conclusion :

The data obtained in the present investigation revealed that high decolourization is achieved with considerable lowering of toxicity. The synthetic dye effluent initially had intense colour and high COD which could successfully be electrolysed for 90–95% colour removal (almost zero absorbance level) and 85% COD removal in a lab scale batch system. The electrochemical treatment process has a potential for developing into efficient and economical technology due to the inherent simplicity of the process and relatively low cost of electrons as reactants.

Experimental

Controlled potential electrolysis (CPE) was carried on BAS CV-27 cyclic voltammograph in connection with a Digital Electronic 2000 Omnigraph X-Y/t recorder. A three-electrode cell system was used for the electrolysis. The

working electrode is platinum foil ($3 \times 3 \text{ cm}^2$) and steel foil ($4.5 \times 3.5 \text{ cm}^2$) the reference is Ag/AgCl and auxiliary electrode a platinum wire that was directly poured in the solution. Cyclic voltammograms were taken using EG & G Princeton Applied Research VersaStat-II Potentiostat. The pH-metric measurements were made on Hach EC-40 Bench top pH/ISE meter.

For identification of end products thin layer chromatography (TLC) was employed using readymade silica gel plates of E. Merck. Components of the electrolysed solution on the TLC plate could be visualised under UV lamp. The reaction kinetics was studied with the help of UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Elico SL-159). The rate of decrease of colour and rate of decrease of current with time were continuously monitored. Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) of both coloured and decolourised/electrolysed solutions were recorded using COD Digestion Apparatus (Spectra lab 2015S).

Reagent and solution : Brilliant blue FCF of Aldrich, USA was used. 2×10^{-4} M stock solution of brilliant blue FCF in double-distilled water was prepared, 1.0 M KCl was used as a supporting electrolyte. BR buffers in the pH range 2.5–12.0 were used. All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

Procedure : For cyclic voltammetry (CV) and controlled potential electrolysis (CPE) the solution was prepared by taking 9.0 ml of the stock solution and 1.0 ml of 1.0 M KCl. The solution was deaerated by passing nitrogen gas for about 15 min and the cyclic voltammograms were recorded in the beginning of the experiment and then the solution was subjected to CPE at -1.20 V which is slightly higher than the peak potential of the dye. Further at the end of electrolysis the voltammograms were also recorded. For TLC studies both coloured and electrolysed solutions were loaded on the plate and then developed in the selected mobile phase.

For coulometric determination of number of electrons n consumed in the reduction, cyclic voltammograms were recorded at a potential slightly higher than peak potential. With the progress of the electrolysis the colour of the solution gradually faded away and the current also decreases exponentially with time and become practically zero after some time. Value of Q (total charge passed in coulombs) was read directly and by the application of $Q = nFN$, where n is the number of electron transferred per molecule, F is the Faraday constant (96500C) and N is the number of moles of substance being electrolyzed.

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